

Strengthening BUMDes as a supporting capacity for the tourism village of Kampung Mojopahit, Mojokerto Regency

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Abstract

The development of a tourist village is one of the mainstay concepts to optimize village development to become an independent village. The type of research used in this research is qualitative approach. Results of the research are Assets managed by BUMDes are grants or equity participation from the Bejijong village government and asset loans to carry out activities. This management is still not optimal due to a pandemic that occurred in the early stages of the reactivation of BUMDes. The inclusion of additional assets will be carried out under the BUMDes building construction scheme which will be used as an operational site as well as business activities. BUMDes have partnered with the community to manage their assets to optimize tourism villages, but they are still not optimally strong due to the lack of tourists arriving during the pandemic. Efforts to strengthen the role of BUMDes in future development need to collaborate with the village government, youth organizations, and other institutions in Bejijong Village, as well as parties outside the village who can contribute to developing the village economy.

Keywords: *BUMDes, Development, Tourist Village*

A. Introduction

The development of a tourist village is one of the mainstay concepts to optimize village development to become an independent village. In developing a tourism village, the village government must have a mature planning design for clear and measurable village development based on the potential of the village itself (Nursetiawan & Garis, 2019). The development of a tourist village is also a complex development that is the same as other developments which cannot be used as a single development. Developing a tourism village also means not only working on tourism objects, but also various other supporting aspects such as access, facilities, infrastructure, and also the community as resources who will manage the place. On the other hand, in developing the community's economy they also need a catalytic role that cannot be carried out by the village directly but uses another entity called Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes).

Tourist village development, several components need to be completed to create a tourist village (Tanaya, 2019), including:

1. Attractions, an overview of the state of the village conditions
2. Accommodation, facilities for tourist residences
3. Facilities, special facilities that are made to meet the needs of tourists.

Figure 1 model of a tourist village Source: Tanaya (2019)

The development of tourism villages has several benefits that can be drawn, so it is very attractive for every village to develop this sector (Hariyoko et al., 2021; Putri et al., 2018; Tanaya, 2019), among them:

1. Provides a multiplier effect on other aspects.
2. Providing employment opportunities for rural communities
3. Develop village potential.
4. Create new business opportunities.
5. Increase PADes
6. Creating village development collaboration with other parties

The role of BUMDes is to provide opportunities to develop the economic potential that exists in the village. The relationship between BUMDes and tourism village development is to provide better and more profitable tourism village management support such as developing superior products, providing accommodation, and improving the quality of human resources managing tourism objects. (Ardhana Putra et al., 2019). In managing the village economy, BUMDes also need to collaborate with various parties who have an interest in certain matters, for example in matters of developing a tourism village it is necessary to work together with a Village Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) (Isnaini & Nawangsari, 2018). Collaboration between these actors will certainly be carried out well if there is a clear and mature plan.

BUMDes is a new creature that is expected to be able to improve and assist in village development. BUMDes will provide new opportunities in creating the village economy and driving the community's economy. Benefit (Eko, 2014) The expected BUMDes include:

1. Providing basic services to the community, especially the poor and women.
2. village income
3. Improve the quality of health
4. Easy credit/loan access.
5. Reducing loan sharks
6. The local community can easily obtain basic needs and inputs, either using credit.
7. The external business has not provided significant benefits.
8. Stimulating the village economy and creating jobs, as well as increasing village and community income.

Bejijong Village is one of the villages in Mojokerto Regency and focuses on becoming a tourism village as a direction for its development. This effort is very realistic because of the village's potential which is suitable for tourism. Tourism in Bejijong village is in the form of the Siti Inggil site, the Mahavihara which has a sleeping Buddha, and the Brahu temple. The development of this tourist site is supported by various businesses of the village community who are aware of tourism by providing accommodation, culinary, and souvenir facilities. The development of the tourist village has succeeded in making Bejijong village one of the best tourist villages in Indonesia (Prihatini, 2021).

The role of BUMDes "Wijaya" in Bejijong village can still be developed further. BUMDes Wijaya already has several business lines that act as a supporting capacity in the development of a tourist village. BUMDes Wijaya is also one of the contributors to Village Original Income (PADes) in 2021 which will receive more than 150 million rupiahs. Efforts to increase PADes, even more, can be done by increasing the role of BUMDes in attracting more tourists and contributing to the benefits of village communities.

The constraints on the role of BUMDES that occur in general are internal and external aspects. On the internal aspect of the problems faced by BUMDes such as management, HR, and organizational governance (Gayo et al., 2020; Syarifudin & Astuti, 2020; Zakariya, 2020). While the external aspects that are still an obstacle are market developments, government policies, and the dynamics of village communities (Hasanah, 2019; Syarifudin & Astuti, 2020). Bejijong Village Businesses that want to develop the potential of existing villages into tourist villages need to pay attention to these various problems to focus on developing BUMDes in the future.

Research on tourist villages has been found in many references, this is due to the widespread development of tourist villages in Indonesia. The community is given a lot of tourist village threats as has been researched by Tanaya (2019), but there is still not much discussion linking BUMDes with the development of tourist villages like the research that has been done by Courtesy (2018) and Achmad Guna et al (2020). The research that will be carried out in Bejijong Village is related to the role capability and optimization of BUMDes in supporting tourism villages that have been formed.

B. Methods

The type of research used in this research is qualitative with this research approach used to obtain more complete data about the research problem. Research focus in accordance with the formulation of the problem and the theory that has been used is as follows: Optimization of village assets to support BUMDes, The role of BUMDes business and its impact on society, and Optimization of BUMDes in developing tourism villages

C. Results and Discussion

The research results that have been obtained are still very raw and still limited in the data aspect, so deeper data mining is needed in the future. An overview of the research results following the research focus as follows:

1. Optimizing village assets to support BUMDes

Optimizing village assets in supporting the BUMDes business unit is by providing an initial investment of 30 million rupiahs. The capital is provided in the form of cash and comes from village funds which have been budgeted for in the 2019 APBDes. The capital is used to purchase business equipment in the form of booths that can be rented by people who want to sell in the space provided. The inclusion of funds from the village government is a positive effort in village development (Pradani, 2020). Innovative efforts in this development also need to consider the potential for profit sharing that will be given to the village government. Additional capital participation in BUMDes is scheduled every year with the construction of a building worth 100 million rupiahs on village government land. The plan is listed in the 2020-2026 RPJMDes.

BUMDes can conduct business analysis before carrying out business activities in the community (Ardhana Putra et al., 2019). BUMDes can be strengthened by the government first with the help of facilities. Facilitation support for the location of business activities using public facilities was carried out when the BUMDes was initially developed. The village government

provides access to sell in public facilities that many people pass through. The initial establishment of the BUMDes was already able to generate profits, but the pandemic has changed the schemes and business plans that have been made by the Wijaya BUMDes. The remaining cash obtained is then rotated by the manager into an online bill payment business unit.

2. The role of BUMDes business and its impact on society

The business units now owned by BUMDes are in the form of online bill payments, homestay accommodation providers, and food providers for village activities. This business was developed by BUMDes Wijaya during the pandemic. The initial business developed as online bill payment. Seeing the potential that exists in the community that can encourage village tourism, then BUMDes also collaborates with MSMEs in the village to develop businesses that provide homestay accommodation locations, and food providers for village activities. Diversity of business is good for expanding the type of business, but it's also a problem if it can't be managed properly (Suparji, 2019). At first, it was felt that the efforts that had been carried out by the BUMDes had received positive support from the village government, but the COVID-19 pandemic caused new problems by hampering global economic activity.

Figure 2 Homestay business managed by BUMDes, Source: Researcher documentation, 2022

The business unit that provides homestay accommodation locations is trying to be used by BUMDes by using the Majapahit model building facilities that have been made through the assistance of the provincial government in residents' residential areas. The existing building was developed and converted into a homestay. The village community that owns the asset then shares the results with the tenants of the building. Collaboration is carried out by sharing profits

between business owners and BUMDes. The profit sharing is agreed upon at the beginning with a small distribution for BUMDes, the profit sharing process must benefit the managing partners so that the BUMDes business can continue well (Firdaus, 2020).

3. Optimization of BUMDes in the development of tourist villages

Existing businesses will be further developed from a managerial perspective by recruiting and developing businesses with young people. The recruited youth will be directed to be active in managing community waste. This management is because the issue of community waste is getting more and more attention. After all, some members of the public dispose of garbage in public areas.

Since the formation of BUMDes Wijaya on October 1 2018, its journey has experienced ups and downs. In 2020, the condition of disrupted social mobility due to the Covid-19 pandemic has hampered BUMDes activities. From internal BUMDes HR factors that lack synergy in carrying out performance and duties as administrators of BUMDes Wijaya Bejjong Village. Some of the factors that make BUMDes less active are the busyness of each administrator and time constraints. From the time it was formed until now, it is necessary to optimize the BUMDes of Bejjong Village to improve in realizing the BUMDes as expected. The improvement plans are:

1. Through Karang Taruna, Bejjong Village BUMDes can carry out discourses that are determined to optimize the existence of BUMDES(Novitasari & Susanto, 2019). Karang Taruna as a forum for young people from Bejjong Village synergizes to help BUMDes carry out superior programs. The first is by forming Environmental Cadres, later environmental cadres will become community mobilizers to be able to manage the selection of dry and wet waste(Gayo et al., 2020). The two Youth Organizations can be involved in BUMDes programs by providing freelance salaries, in addition to forming business units with the Youth Organization scheme as the main mover. Third, with the current conditions of the Industrial Revolution 5.0 where digital sophistication makes it easier to convey all information. Karang Taruna as a young generation that is certainly very attached to digital sophistication can manage Bejjong Village as a tourism village and a village that cares about the environment.
2. One of the obstacles faced by the Bejjong Village BUMDes is that the BUMDes legal entity has not yet been formed, the legal basis that guides BUMDes activities is that only an SK is formed(Kuncahyo, 2018). Then BUMDes administrators do not get a salary because the provisions for issuing a minimum salary are that BUMDes can have a salary of 10,000,000 or more a month. The hope with this is to find the maximum

solution. The BUMDes management themselves think that for this BUMDes must have a business and PPOB, for example, the program they already have is the Kampoeng Majapahit market. In its journey, the Kampoeng Majapahit Market has only been realized 3 times and is currently not running.

3. Other programs that the BUMDes management wants to develop are the Waste Program which is managed by PPOB through the Waste Bank program as a support for Tourism Villages with the help of PKK and Waste management with the help of Karang Taruna. This collaboration with other actors will be carried out properly because basically those who will become partners have the same goal in terms of village development results.(Spekkink & Boons, 2016). Strengthening this collaboration can be done through village consultative meetings and can carry out routine accountability, thereby providing a common perception and goal(Rasanathan et al., 2017).

This optimization of the BUMDes role needs to be assisted by the Bejjong village government. This plan has also been included in the Bejjong Village RPJMDes for the 2020 to 2026 period. Increasing the HR capacity of BUMDes managers and

D. Conclusion

Temporary conclusions that can be drawn from the results of existing research are as follows:

1. Assets managed by BUMDes are grants or equity participation from the Bejjong village government and asset loans to carry out activities. This management is still not optimal due to a pandemic that occurred in the early stages of the reactivation of BUMDes. The inclusion of additional assets will be carried out under the BUMDes building construction scheme which will be used as an operational site as well as business activities.
2. BUMDes have partnered with the community to manage their assets to optimize tourism villages, but they are still not optimally strong due to the lack of tourists arriving during the pandemic.
3. Efforts to strengthen the role of BUMDes in future development need to collaborate with the village government, youth organizations, and other institutions in Bejjong Village, as well as parties outside the village who can contribute to developing the village economy.

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